

THE
CTENIDAE
OF
SOUTH AFRICA

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South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide Ctenidae 2021 Version 1 :1-17

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ABSTRACT

The family Ctenidae occurs worldwide and is represented by 47 genera and 525 species. The Ctenidae of South Africa is in need of a revision. Presently three genera *Africactenus*, *Anahita* and *Ctenus* are recognized from seven known species. Undetermined species of *Anahita* are housed in the National Museum in Bloemfontein and the National Collection of Arachnida. Four species are South African endemics: *Ctenus corniger* F.O.P.-Cambridge, 1898, *C. gulosus* Des Arts, 1912, *C. parvoculatus* Benoit, 1979 and *C. transvaalensis* Benoit, 1981 and the rest have a wide distribution and is listed as Least Concern. But the identification of the family is still a problem and of the 447 records in the National Collection of Arachnida more than 48 % are not identified.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank the Agricultural Research Council (ARC) and the South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI) Threatened Species Programme; the Universities of the Free State, Venda and Pretoria; the National Research Foundation (NRF) for generously funding and support. The staff of the Arachnology section at the National Collection of Arachnida (Connie Anderson, Petro Marais, Sma Mathebula, Robin Lyle and Annette van den Berg), as well as several volunteers from the public, are thanked for their assistance with the sorting and databasing of specimens collected during the SANSA surveys. Various students, members of the public and the Spider Club of Southern Africa collected material for SANSA. We also thank the South African National Parks and E. Oppenheimer & Son for support and providing opportunity to collect in the parks and reserves as well as the provincial conservation agencies for collecting permits. We are especially thankful to all the photographers who provided photographs for the SANSA Virtual Museum without their contribution this guide would have not been possible.

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* SPECIES LISTED IN WORLD SPIDER CATALOG (2020) FROM SOUTH AFRICA

Ctenid eye pattern Photo Peter Webb

Ctenus sp. in burrow Photo Erika

FAMILY CTENIDAE Keyserling, 1877

The family Ctenidae occurs worldwide and is represented by 47 genera and 525 species (World Spider Catalog 2020). From South Africa three genera and seven species are known. Some species are still undescribed.

COMMON NAMES: Tropical Wolf Spiders

MORPHOLOGY: Body size: 5-40 mm (males slightly smaller and more slender). Colour brown to fawn, with patterns or spots on the abdomen. Carapace ovoid with a deep depression or elevated in the region of the fovea; eight eyes in three rows 2:4:2 or sometimes 4:2:2. Abdomen ovoid, longer than wide; sometimes with a median band, patterns or rows of spots. Legs strong and stout with spines; tarsi with scopulae and two claws; tibiae I have numerous pairs of ventral spines (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014; Jocqué & Steyn 1997).

LIFE STYLE: They are free-living nocturnal ground hunters commonly found under fallen logs. When running the front legs are usually held off the ground. One species, *Ctenus pulchiventris*, is the dominant wandering spider found in Afromontane forests in KwaZulu-Natal. Females of the genera *Africactenus* and *Ctenus* deposit their egg sac on the substrate or carry it between her chelicera and palp (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997).

TAXONOMY: Southern African species not revised.

KEY TO THE SOUTH AFRICAN GENERA

1. Carapace with a group of converging hairs originating from between posterior median eyes; male palpal tibia without retrolateral apophysis; epigyne with membranous areas, often round in shape**Anahita**
 - Carapace without converging hairs between posterior median eyes, at the most with a cluster of parallel hairs; male palpal tibia with retrolateral tibial apophysis; epigyne with solid plate or otherwise different**2**

2. Tibia I and II without a terminal pair of spines; carapace with indentation, deepest point in front of fovea; dorsum of abdomen with well-developed hair tufts**Africactenus**
 - Tibia I and II with a terminal pair of spines; carapace without indentation and abdomen with hair tufts less developed.....**Ctenus**

Ctenidae. a: undescribed genus, female, dorsal view; b: line-drawing showing leg lengths; c: Cteninae, eye pattern, dorsal view; d: Acantheinae, eye pattern, anterior view; e: Cteninae (*Ctenus* spp.), carapace, lateral view; f: Acantheinae (*Anahita* spp.) carapace in lateral view, showing depression; g: epigyne, showing horns; h: male palp, ventral view, showing cup-shaped median apophysis (after Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997).

UNDETERMINED SPECIES

GENUS *ANAHITA* Karsch, 1879

MORPHOLOGY: Carapace with tuft of converging hairs implanted between posterior median eyes; posterior median eyes nearly double the size of anterior median eye; male palp without retrolateral apophysis; embolus with peculiar shape and large median apophysis. The female is characterized by the epigyne having a bottle-shaped septum.

Eyes *Anahita* sp. after Steyn et al. 2003

Anahita sp. epigynum Photo Peter Webb

Anahita sp. 1 National Museum Bloemfontein Photo L. Lotz

Anahita sp. 2 National Museum Bloemfontein Photo L. Lotz

Anahita sp. from Ellisras Photos Peter Webb

Anahita sp. from Legalametse Photo Peter Webb

GENUS *AFRICACTENUS* Hyatt, 1954

The genus *Africactenus* described by Hyatt (1954) contains 21 species, of which 20 are African endemics. Only one species so far recorded from South Africa.

COMMON NAMES: African Tropical Wolf Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Africactenus agillior* (Pocock, 1900)

MORPHOLOGY: Carapace with deep dorsal indentation; clypeus high; cheliceral retromargin with four teeth; eyes 2-4-2; second row of eyes slightly procurved; median ocular quadrangle about as long as wide; anterior median eyes smaller and closer to each other than posterior median eyes; clypeus equal to or wider than diameter of anterior median eyes; labium longer than wide, notched at the base as in *Ctenus*. Abdomen ovoid, longer than wide; sometimes with a median band, patterns or rows of spots; dorsum of abdomen with **well-developed hair tufts**. Legs with anterior tibia with 5-6 pairs of ventral spines and usually more than one pair of lateral spines; tibia I and II without a terminal pair of spines. Epigyne deeply emarginated anteriorly, resulting in the formation of two anteriorly projecting lobes (Hyatt 1954; Steyn et al. 2003).

LIFE STYLE: Free-living ground dwellers.

TAXONOMY: Genus last revised by Hyatt (1954).

after Hyatt (1954)

Africactenus after Steyn et al. 2003

Africactenus sp. Photo P. Webb

Africactenus tridentatus Hyatt, 1954

COMMON NAME: Africa ctenus Tropical Wolf Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Hyatt (1954) from Mashonaland, Zimbabwe. The species was also more recently collected from South Africa, and is known from two provinces (EOO= 8 km²; AOO= 8 km²; 16-874 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species is a free-running ground dweller known from the Savanna and Fynbos biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Zimbabwe. New: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Jeffreys Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Addo National park (-33.32, 25.72). *Mpumalanga:* White River (-25.31, 31.02).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No conservation actions are recommended. Species protected in the Addo National park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Benoit (1974). Known only from the male.

Palp after Hyatt (1954)

Africactenus tridentatus male from Nelspruit
Photo Aart Louw

Africactenus tridentatus Photo Peter Webb

GENUS *CTENUS* Walckenaer, 1805

The genus *Ctenus* described by Walckenaer (1805) is represented by 225 species (World Spider Catalogue 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Ctenus Tropical Wolf Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Ctenus dubius* Walckenaer, 1805

MORPHOLOGY: Body size: 15–20 mm. Colour: brown to fawn, carapace with wide pale lateral margin; radiating striae do not reach edge; abdomen with pattern or spots dorsally usually darker ventrally with double row of sigilla. Carapace highest in region of fovea; eyes eight in three rows (2:4:2); anterior lateral eyes between posterior median and posterior lateral eyes; eyes in anterior row small; posterior row strongly recurved; clypeus high; chelicerae strong with 4–5 teeth; mouthparts with endites converging slightly. Abdomen ovoid, longer than wide; sometimes with median stripe, chevron pattern or rows of spots. Legs strong and stout, with spines and scopulae; anterior tibiae with 3–6 pairs of ventral spines; tarsi with two claws (Steyn et al. 2003).

LIFE STYLE: They are free-living nocturnal hunters commonly found under fallen logs. Sometimes found in burrows. When running, the front legs are usually held off the ground. They hunt their prey on low-growing foliage and on the ground. In *Ctenus* the female deposits her egg sac on the substrate or carries it between her chelicerae and palpi. Ctenids are abundant in forests and surrounding areas, dominating the nocturnal spider fauna there. They are regularly collected using pitfall traps, or by sweep-netting low-growing foliage or night-collecting by hand.

TAXONOMY: South African species not revised.

Ctenus sp. eye pattern Steyn et al. 2003

Epigyne photo T. Bird

Ctenus sp. from Legalametse Photo: P. Webb

Ctenus caligineus des Arts, 1912

COMMON NAME: Zaire Tropical Wolf Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1912 from Zaïre. The species sampled from three African countries but is expected to occur in more countries. Recently sampled for the first time from South Africa from Limpopo and protected in the Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (EOO= <1000 km²; AOO= 8 km²; 574-1002 m a.s.l.). Due to wide geographical range listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species is a free-running ground dweller known from the Savanna Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Zaïre, Burundi. New: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Farm Malta (-24.1617, 30.2538); Ndengeza (-23.317, 30.411).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Receive some protection in the Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2016). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Benoit (1977). Known from both sexes.

Ctenus caligineus female from Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve Photo sPeter Webb

Epigynum after Benoit (1977)

Palp after Benoit (1979)

Ctenus corniger F.O.P.-Cambridge, 1898

COMMON NAME: Natal Tropical Wolf Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 1898 from type locality only given as Natal. Although drawings were provided by Benoit (1979) species identification still problematic. Too little is known about the location, habitat and threats of this taxon for an assessment to be made. It is therefore listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reason.

LIFE STYLE: The species is a free-running ground dweller.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: KwaZulu-Natal no exact locality.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Data deficient and more sampling is needed, as well as re-description of type material.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Benoit (1979). Known only from the male.

Palp after Benoit (1979)

Ctenus gulosus Des Arts, 1912

COMMON NAME: Tropical Wolf Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic, described in 1912 from type locality Durban. The species is known from four provinces, including eight protected areas (EOO= 483 761 km²; AOO= 132 km²; 17-1551 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species is a ground dweller, sampled in pitfall traps from the Forest, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Jeffreys Bay (-34.04, 24.94); Addo National Park (-33.32, 25.72). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45); Nongoma State Forest (-27.93, 32.65); Mkuzi Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Richards Bay (15 km N) (-28.78, 32.1); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Midlands, Good Hope plantation, Boston (-29.6508, 29.9761); Maybole plantation, Richmond (-29.7592, 30.2579). **Mpumalanga:** Barberton (-25.79, 31.04); Kruger National Park: Skukuza (-25, 31.97); Kruger National Park: Satara (-24.38, 31.78); Kruger National Park: Sabiepoort 11 (-25.19, 32.2); Kruger National Park: Pretoriusskop, Shabeni (-25.123, 31.21); Kruger National Park: Vutome 06 (-25.24, 32.08); Kruger National Park: Lwakahle 08 (-25.43, 31.75). **Limpopo:** Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Lephahlale/Ellisras (-23.67, 27.71); Nwanedi Nature Reserve (-22.59, 30.36).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in areas such as Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006); Addo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020); Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2015); Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020) and Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad et al. 2010). No conservation actions are needed.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female.

Ctenus gulosus female from Lephahlale Photos Peter Webb

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Epigynum after Benoit (1979)

Ctenus gulosus female from Lephahlale Photo ASD

Ctenus parvoculatus Benoit, 1979

COMMON NAME: Cave Tropical Wolf Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 1979 from the Table Mountain Echo Hall Caves. The species is known from five provinces including two protected areas: Kosi Bay Nature Reserve and Table Mountain National Park (EOO=783 589 km²; AOO= 60 km²; 7-1583 m a.s.l.). There are no known threats to the species. Due to its wide geographical distribution, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species is known from caves and forest areas in the Fynbos, Forest, Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013), Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Savanna (Foord et al. 2011) and Thicket biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** East London (-33.01, 27.9); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61); Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91); King William's Town (-32.88, 27.39); Queenstown (-31.89, 26.85). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); Nkandla Forest (-28.61, 31.09); Umbilo (-29.88, 30.96). **Limpopo:** Makapansgat (-24.15, 29.18); Beitbridge (-22.2, 29.99). **Mpumalanga:** Echo Caves (-23.33, 30.63); Serunecjar Caves (-24.65, 30.32); Dry Tiger Caves near Pilgrims Rest (-26.78, 28.77). **Western Cape:** Table Mountain National Park (Echo Hall Caves) (-33.82, 18.48).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the Table Mountain National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Myburg 2009; Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020), Nkandla Forest, Kosi Bay Nature Reserve and Tiger Caves near Pilgrims Rest (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Myburg 2009). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female.

Epigyne after Benoit (1979)

Epigyne Photo ASD

Eye pattern after Benoit (1979)

Ctenus parvoculatus female Photos

Ctenus pulchriventris (Simon, 1897)

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

COMMON NAME: Tropical Wolf Spider

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic, described in 1897 from Zimbabwe. From South Africa, it has been collected from four provinces including seven protected areas (EOO= 762 705 km²; AOO= 92 km²; 7-1583 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species is a ground dweller, sampled in pitfall traps in the Forest, Indian Coastal Belt, Savanna (Foord et al. 2011) and Thicket biomes. It has also been collected in crops such as citrus, maize, pine, plantations and strawberries (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** East London (-33.01, 27.9); Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); King William's Town (-32.88, 27.39); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61); Queenstown (-31.89, 26.85); Thomas Baines Nature Reserve (-33.36, 19.31). **Limpopo:** Beitbridge (-22.2, 29.99); Makapansgat (-24.15, 29.18); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-23.12, 29.00); Vyeboom (-23.144, 30.380); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16). **Mpumalanga:** Crocodile Valley Estate (-25.47, 31.03); Dry Tiger cave near Pilgrims Rest (-26.78, 28.77). **KwaZulu-Natal:** iSimangaliso National Park: Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); Lake Sibaya (-27.35, 32.7); Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45); Nkandla Forest (-28.61, 31.09); Umbilo (-29.88, 30.96); Umfolozi Drift (-28.3, 31.76); Duduku Forest (-28.37, 32.23); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); Kloof (-29.78, 30.83).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in seven reserves such as Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2016), Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019) and Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve. Also sampled from several caves (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Myburg 2009). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

Ctenus pulchriventris male from Kloof Photo Peter Webb

Epigynum after Benoit (1979)

18
Palp after Benoit (1979)

Palp photo ASD)

Ctenus spectabilis Lessert, 1921

COMMON NAME: Tropical Wolf spider.

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1921 from Tanzania. The species is known from the four African countries. From South Africa only known from the Northern Cape (EOO=4 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 1172 m a.s.l.). Due to wide geographical range listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Free living ground dweller that was sampled with pitfall traps from the Grassland Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Tanzania, Uganda, Zaire. New: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Northern Cape: Benfontein Nature Reserve(-28.82, 24.82).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the Benfontein Nature Reserve. Due to wide geographical range no conservation actions are needed.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Benoit (1979). Known from both sexes

19
Palp after Benoit (1979)

5
Epigynum after Benoit (1979)

Ctenus spectabilis male Photos: ASD

Ctenus transvaalensis Benoit, 1981

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

COMMON NAME: Transvaal Tropical Wolf Spider

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 1981, from a male from Woodbush in Limpopo. The species is known from four provinces including six protected areas (EOO= 171 730 km²; AOO= 52 km²; 256-1516 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical distribution, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species is a ground dweller living in burrows without trapdoors in the Savanna (Foord et al. 2011) and Grassland biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.8, 28.77); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Kloof (-29.78,30.83). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Springbok Flats: Tuinplaas (-24.56, 28.46); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Pietersburg district, Woodbush(-23.89, 29.46) Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99,29.04); Lekgalameetsi Nature Reserve Haffenden Heights. (-23.82, 30.16). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park: Lwakahle (-25.43, 31.75); Kruger National Park: Vutome (-25.24,32.08); Kruger National Park: Makhuthwanini (-25.38, 31.6); Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in areas such as Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord et al 2016); Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020) and Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2008) and Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the male.

After Benoit (1981)

Ctenus transvaalensis male from Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve Photo Peter Webb

Ctenus transvaalensis palp Photo ASD

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